

ANALYSIS OF CHARACTERISTICS OF HEROES IN THE PROSE WORKS OF SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAEV

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Abstract. *In the given article the heroes of the works of Shukur Kholmirzaev are presented as the representatives of realistic literature. Certain personalities were the basis for them or attracted the attention of the writer and inspired him. Undoubtedly, the writer often became a real source of his own life. This article examines the analysis of the characters of the heroes of the writer's several stories.*

Keywords: *character of heroes, realistic images, character and images, psyche, human nature, thematic volume, system of images, ideological orientation, prose skill.*

It is important to mention that People's Writer of Uzbekistan, laureate of the State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Khamza, Shukur Kholmirzaev is one of our writers who made a worthy contribution to the development of Uzbek literature. Aesthetic categories in fiction are inextricably linked with the art of depicting the image of a person. Indeed, the main goal of literature, which determines its own characteristics, is to describe various spiritual experiences of a person, his spiritual world, his place in life and his aspirations. For this reason, academician Izzat Sultan wrote: "In a work of art consisting of anthropology, we are witnesses to the description of people with different levels of detail and depth" [7, 191].

Definitely, the image of a person depicted in a work of art is the concept of a hero. A specific product of the writer's aesthetic attitude to life events or to a certain category of people in his work of art is expressed in the form of a hero or a system of images. The concept of a hero is also used in literary criticism with the terms character or image.

According to I. Sultan: "The character is the bearer of the author's aesthetic ideal" [7, 191]. In the dictionary of literary terms, the specific features of the character as a literary phenomenon are explained as follows: "It becomes more and more complex, colorful and improving in connection with the development of society and the growth of artistic thinking.

This situation, in turn, is associated with the development of methods and possibilities for creating characters. For example, in a folk epic, a character is created on the basis of a social ideal, while in the literature of the modern era, it is created without repetition, rich in individual characteristics" [11, 348]. Thus, the character of the hero of fiction appears in its own way in the literature of the current period. We can clearly see this in the example of the system of images and heroes of modern Uzbek prose.

The images of Sh. Kholmirzaev strengthened the spirit of the heroes of Uzbek fairy tales, especially the lack of self-satisfaction and the desire for deeper self-realization. In this sense, the main goal of the writer is not to describe the actions of his heroes in public life, but their intellect.

According to the author's plan, intellect is the axis of the hero. For this reason, the writer is more interested in the actions of the hero, and not the result of the event based on the work, and the disclosure of the processes of the hero's intellect in relation to this event and result. In such cases, some of the stories of Sh. Kholmirzaev and the characters in them leave the impression that

the reader or critic, and sometimes even the author of the work, has a contradictory attitude that has not received a clear resolution. In particular, the same can be said about the story "Once".

Besides that, the endless fluctuations in the heart of the young driver O'sar - the exploration of his own soul, the instability of the inner world, the past and the present, his views on himself and his wife, as a result of which his mother was taken on a journey to distant places, and then the process of mental suffering that passed through his body - are the hero's attempt at self-realization.

In the story "Once Upon a Time" the writer was one of the first in our literature to artistically embody the impact of these recent changes and difficulties on the human soul.

It is not a secret that the situation has reached such a level that even the character of the villagers, whose age-old traditions and customs are very strong and whose habits are not easy to change, has begun to change. This is due to the influence of family, environment, lack of circumstances, helplessness, nervous conditions. According to the story "As it was in ancient times", some of these changes were not noticeable in the nature of the people until recently. Mum raised her grandson by herself. Due to the hard times, the difficulty of earning money, poverty, the language of the daughter-in-law, and the fact that the speech at home does not correspond to the street, chaos reigns in the family every day. On top of that, Mum is getting old and losing his mind. As if this were not enough, the stinking patient was tortured. So, nervousness in the family, at home, the situation is difficult, the sky is far away, the earth is heavy.

No matter how patient Osar was, no matter how hard it was for him, the situation and conditions turned his nature to change. The old man with black eyes felt that he was doing too much for himself, his existence and his wife. As a result, the devil will go astray and destroy the strong national unity that has been preserved for centuries. One day, O'sar leaves his mother in deserted places, where she cannot return. The fact is that the young man's nerves could not withstand the marital suffering.

However, the writer does not end his work here. Because his goal is not only to show the severity of the times, the spiritual change of the hero, but also to show that human love for a person in the heart of the nation, in the spirit of the nation never fades.

The reader cannot hide his hatred for Osar and his wife. At the same time, without realizing it, he begins to analyze the circumstances that led them to this situation, and comes to the correct conclusion that such an attitude towards his mother is impossible. The carpenter and his wife realize their bitter mistake: they decided to bring their mother back.

At this point, the writer brings the narrative to its climax. Mum is gone. He was taken away by unknown, kind people. Is it possible to bear these pangs of conscience? Thus, the writer condemns his heroes to this kind of eternal punishment for their actions.

At the end of a literary work, a great meaning is absorbed. Other people take Mum to their shelter. It should be understood that the main burden of the idea of the work lies, in a certain sense, on these people. As long as there are such people who are almost not shown and do not participate in history, life does not fade away, love does not die, and the nation is not humiliated.

Sh. Kholmiraev creates the color (spirit) of time and space in artistic language, showing his character through zamzams in the spiritual world, the simplicity and spontaneity of the heroes, not fitting into the rules of "porim", being able to have a bold critical attitude to society. A. Kadiri is the predecessor of writers who continue their traditions and elevate them in new conditions. Shukur Kholmiraev has a story called "Fees" written in a heroic style. Some people may agree or disagree with this opinion, but it can be said that the creation of this story was strongly influenced

by "The Thief" by Abdulla Kahhor. Of course, the similarity is not that both stories tell about a bull. It is about the closeness and commonality of artistic logic, the development of the creative principles of the master writer by the student in terms of creating characters. In "Fees", old man Ostanakul causes the unclean death of an ox on the collective farm. Not because of indifference or coldness to his work, no, on the contrary. For many years, this bull has lightened the burden of old Ostanakul, shared his many sorrows and joys. In short, witness many sweet and bitter memories. This bull accidentally falls seriously ill and goes into convulsions. If old man Ostanakul had a hand in the slaughter. The old man tried to do this several times, but his heart did not give in. As a result, the shepherd Ostanakul is forced to pay the collective farm for feed for the bulls. In this picture, we now encounter the second magnetic field of the work, which has a strong effect on the reader.

"The head of the department stood up in protest:

- Father, that's all. You will pay for the bull! - He looked at the people around him one by one. - It is believed that he killed on purpose.

The shy old man slowly raised his head:

- Okay, son, we will pay.

- Just don't hesitate! You are not poor, you have a strong back, you have relatives. Has anyone taken your old lady? So be it... The meeting is over!" [9, 295-301]

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the old man slowly raised his head and in a broken voice agreed to pay for the bull's food. At this point we feel as if we have seen Grandfather Cain. Everyone knows why the old women of Shorkhi collect five to ten coins at the end of their lives. We are familiar with these people who take what they have accumulated for the sake of birth and death. Aren't the people who held a meeting with those who did worse and sentenced old Ostanakul to find grandfather Kain's lost bull the same types of two eras, as if the peasants had nothing in common with the heart? Grandfather Kabul, what relation do these bosses have to old Ostanakul's heart in "Fees" and the reason for the premature death of the ox? Shukur Kholmiraev's novel "The Last Stop" invites you to observe with its proximity to real life.

In this novel, Nasir reveals step by step the reasons for human happiness and unhappiness through the relationship between Sadik and Munira. First of all, a person must trust and rely on his partner. And Sadik does not trust people, he treats everyone with suspicion. As a result, the nature of these two images is opposite to each other. One of them enjoys nature, and the other considers it normal to hurt animals. The world itself consists of these two opposing forces. One enjoys pain, and the other enjoys pleasure. The result, as a product of the writer's skill, is a very impressive picture of mental suffering. Indeed, the fact that against all actions of the heart there is its opposite - the evil of the heart - fills the reader with deep reflection.

The title "The Last Station", as the author notes, is symbolic. Since a person is doomed to various trials and difficulties, happiness and unhappiness, happy and sad days during his life, he should carefully and skillfully describe the processes of transition from one station to another. The writer acted according to this conviction. The heroes of the novel reflect only one stop in life. If we take into account that life goes on, that it will have new demands and desires, we will understand that the writer did not in vain interfere with the fates of the heroes, did not make a subjective judgment about them, did not leave a final conclusion for the reader in vain. [8,208]

In "The Last Station", images of intellectuals with a clear conscience and an open heart, searching for their identity, are collected in an ensemble. They begin to wonder who we are, whose

descendants we are. The main topics of conversation will be Uzbek clans, the ancient history of the country and ancient culture. The spiritual and social life of society is truly reflected in the work. With his first novel, the writer denies the literary norms and standards of his time. He wants to prove that literary creativity is different from journalism and publicism, that a writer must study the human heart. We do not say that he denies this in vain and tries to secretly emphasize it. The reason is that the period of writing and publishing the novel was the era of socialist realism. It was impossible to doubt this path.

The old woman has been relying on her daughter-in-law till her death. The family built by his son Mamarajab and daughter-in-law Nasiba was born without a building. The head of the family, Oktam, does not consider himself guilty of destroying this young family. The teacher Akhadova lives alone in Termez because her husband is a military man. Her three sons are in the city. Her female dream is to have a whole family.

As we have already said above, at first glance, the family crisis and disorganization, which is the peace of society, are not clearly visible. But you can see that families, which are considered small units in the socialist system, have somehow found themselves on the brink of an abyss. The situation of this episode and the characters of the novel does not leave the reader indifferent. The reader pities one of them, sympathizes with one and hates the other. Because the novel presents you with a living, real person: you do not see a fictitious, polished image. The writer opens his overflowing heart, and the reader sees a real work, born under the moon and day.

By summerising it should be considered that the transition from the short story to the novel genre has yielded good results in improving the writer's creativity. This is one of the important factors in the poetics of Shukur Kholmiraev's oeuvre.

From this point of view, the conflicts of the period in his interpretation are of great importance in the fate of images. Stories and novellas served as leaven for his large-scale works. This is also a tool that ensures the success of the artist's works.

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